

Favipiravir-indomethacin interaction and its impact on their solid-state character

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Abstract

Favipiravir is an antiviral agent, a weak acid, and slightly soluble in water, while indomethacin is a weak basic compound and a poorly water-soluble anti-inflammatory drug. This study aimed to combine the two drugs as an eutectics mixture system to enhance their physicochemical properties. The study began with a phase diagram constructed from thermal analyses using electrothermal data, elaborated with differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), powder X-ray diffractometry (PXRD), Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, and electron microscopic observation. The mixture was then evaluated for its solubility characteristics. The unique profile of the phase diagram indicated a melting point lower than those of the starting materials, at 144 °C, observed at a 1:2 molar ratio of favipiravir–indomethacin. DSC also showed a single endothermic curve at the same temperature. Subsequently, the PXRD and FTIR data revealed no new physical or chemical phases, confirming a simple eutectic interaction between the antiviral and anti-inflammatory agents, which is rare in drug–drug interactions. However, the solubility tests showed significant improvement, particularly for indomethacin, which exhibited up to a 100-fold increase in solubility. The change in particle form and size was predicted as the mechanism responsible for the increased solubility, which was then confirmed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Imaging confirmed that favipiravir coats the surface of indomethacin, reducing interfacial tension. Smaller particle sizes are likely to increase surface area and solubility, potentially enhancing bioavailability and accelerating the onset of action. These findings support the development of a solid-state antiviral–anti-inflammatory drug combination.

Keywords

antiviral, anti-inflammatory drug, eutectic system, favipiravir, indomethacin

Introduction

Favipiravir is a first-choice antiviral for treating COVID-19 in Indonesia. Delivering antiviral medications with anti-inflammatory therapies is a standard treatment for viral infections (Pilkington et al. 2020). This approach aims to optimize patient outcomes by addressing both the viral attack and the associated inflammatory response (Fael and Demirel 2021). Based on its chemical

formula $C_5H_4FN_3O_2$, favipiravir has a molecular weight of 157.1 g/mol and is slightly soluble in water at 2 mg/L. Meanwhile, the anti-inflammatory drug indomethacin, with the chemical formula $C_{19}H_{16}ClNO_4$, has a molecular weight of 357.8 g/mol and is slightly soluble in water at 0.937 mg/L (Ahmad et al. 2023; Ashrafi et al. 2024; Kebler et al. 2024). Solid-state engineering is one of the promising strategies to improve the physicochemical properties of drugs, including the creation of multicomponent drug–

drug systems, which can enhance solubility and stability (Silva et al. 2020; Ngilirabanga nda Samsodien 2021).

Combining both drugs in one solid structure was considered interesting and expected to increase the solubility of the anti-inflammatory agent (Leng et al. 2022). Mixing the two compounds without altering pharmacological activity through non-covalent bonds may enhance the physicochemical properties of the drug (Nugrahani et al. 2018). The interaction between two compounds in a binary system can be identified by constructing a phase diagram. A simple eutectic will exhibit a melting point lower than those of its individual components (Fael and Demirel 2021). Meanwhile, two or more co-melting peaks indicate other types of interaction, such as salt or co-crystal formation, which can be confirmed through further analyses such as PXRD and FTIR. A eutectic mixture does not alter the structure of the multicomponent compounds. Therefore, no new solid-state characteristics are typically observed, apart from thermal behavior, which distinguishes it from other multicomponent systems (Nugrahani et al. 2022).

This experiment aimed to investigate the solid-state interaction between favipiravir and indomethacin and its impact on solubility (Babashkina et al. 2021; Cui et al. 2023). Favipiravir is a compound with a pKa of approximately 5.1 and is slightly soluble in water (2 mg/mL at 25 °C). Based on the favipiravir structure in Fig. 1a, the preferential site for protonation is at the ring nitrogen ortho to the alcohol functional group, followed by protonation of the oxygen on the amide side-chain under more acidic conditions (pKa \approx 4.5) (Lucas 2016; FDA Drug Approval: Indomethacin 2021; Tuesuwan et al. 2022; Rebbaniboni et al. 2023).

On the other hand, indomethacin, whose structure is shown in Fig. 1b, is a lipophilic non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) (Borrajo et al. 2024), with a solubility of only 0.937 mg/L at 25 °C (Fael and Demirel 2021). It functions by inhibiting prostaglandin synthesis produced by cyclooxygenase enzymes and is commonly used to treat fever, pain, and inflammation (Gunaydin and Bilge 2018). The pKa of indomethacin ranges from 3 to 4.5. Within this range, most indomethacin molecules will dissociate into the ionized form, allowing them to cross cell membranes (Reinebrant et al. 2015; Jarman et al. 2022; Sasaki et al. 2024).

The chemical structures of favipiravir and indomethacin are shown in Fig. 1 below:

Figure 1. Structure of favipiravir (a) and indomethacin (b).

Based on their structure, the pair of weak acidic or basic favipiravir-indomethacin was predicted to interact to improve solubility.

Materials and methods

Materials

This study used pharmaceutical-grade favipiravir (PT. Shamparindo, Tbk, Semarang, Indonesia), 98% indomethacin (Tokyo Chemical Industry), absolute pure analysis ethanol (Merck, Indonesia), weighing paper, filter paper, Whatman No. 1, aqua demineralization (DM) prepared by Bandung Institute of Technology (Bandung, Indonesia), pure analysis ethanol from Sigma (Bandung, Indonesia), and capillary pipets (Sakura, Medica, Bandung, Indonesia).

Methods

Phase diagram arrangement

The phase diagram of this experiment is based on the electrothermal melting point data from a series of molar fraction of favipiravir in the mixture with indomethacin, as shown in Fig. 2. Each sample was placed in a capillary tube and positioned in the sample holder. The melting point was measured and visually observed through an observation

Figure 2. Phase diagram construction of favipiravir-indomethacin.

hole. The heating rate was set at 20 °C/min, starting from 100 °C until the phase change appeared. Data were plotted into a phase diagram with the molar ratio on the x-axis and melting point on the y-axis (Nugrahani et al. 2019a, 2019b).

The phase diagram was then confirmed using a DSC instrument (Rigaku Thermoplus EVO2-DSC8231, Tokyo, Japan).

Eutectic mixture

The favipiravir–indomethacin mixture was put in the porcelain mortar at a 1:2 composition. Ethanol absolut was dropped, ground homogeneously, and the method is known as solvent dropped grinding. A small of the dried mixture was recrystallized to observe the crystal form change compared to the single components under 40 × magnification using optical binocular microscope (olympus CX21, Tokyo, Japan). Then, the remaining mixture was characterized using DSC, PXRD, and FTIR.

Solid-state characterization

DSC

A small sample at the critical molar ratio point was placed in an aluminum pan and sealed tightly. Next, the pan was put into the DSC heat flux at a temperature of 30 °C–250 °C with a heating rate of 20 °C/min, and the data were recorded.

PXRD

PXRD was conducted to investigate any new solid-state structures produced. A 30–50 mg sample was placed in the PXRD sample holder (Rigaku Miniflex, Tokyo, Japan), weighed, inserted into the instrument, and analyzed with a Cu (K α) radiation source. PXRD was set at 40 kV and 15 mA, measured in the angle range of $2\theta = 3^{\circ}$ – 60° . The data were processed using Excel 2003.

FTIR

FTIR was done to confirm the possibility of interaction. The sample was measured using FTIR (Jasco 4200 Type-A, Oklahoma City, USA) by mixing 1 mg of the sample with 100 mg of KBr crystals and pressed it with a hydraulic press to create a clear pellet. The pellet was then placed in the sample holder of the FTIR instrument and measured in the range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} . The results of the single compounds and the favipiravir–indomethacin mixture were recorded and overlaid.

SEM

SEM was conducted to examine particle morphology and size. This analysis was performed to observe changes in the habit and size of samples. Before the experiment, the sample was dried, then taken with a spatula spoon as needed, and coated through a coating process. It was then flattened using a hand blower. The imaging process on the SEM was conducted by scanning an electron beam on the focused surface with magnification up to specific scales (100, 200, 300, 400, and so forth).

Analysis of the UV-visible derivative spectrophotometry method

First, standard solutions of favipiravir, indomethacin, and the mixture (1:2 molar ratio) were prepared. They were measured using a UV/Vis diode array spectrophotometer (HP 8453, Canada, USA). The absorbance spectrum was measured and derived mathematically. The best spectrum for each compound that did not overlap was then selected. A series of solution concentrations in water were prepared, and their absorbance at the λ maximum was measured to construct a calibration curve. The validation parameters were checked, including linearity, accuracy, precision, limit of detection and quantification, and range (Nugrahani et al. 2019a, 2019b). This validated method was used in the solubility test. Absorption on the first derivative was read for favipiravir. If the absorption was still concentrated, dilution and re-measurement were carried out until an appropriate concentration was obtained. Solubility (mg/mL) was calculated using the calibration curve. Linearity of the curves was checked ($r \geq 0.997$), with the appropriate accuracy and precision.

Analysis of solubility

The sample was dissolved in aquadest and shaken until powder remained in the solution, indicating saturation. Sampling was done every hour for 4 h, and the solution was then left to settle for 24 h. The solution was filtered, and the filtrate was taken and measured using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer at the previously determined distinctive wavelength (zero derivation) for indomethacin.

Results

Phase diagram construction using electrothermal measurement

The phase diagram of the favipiravir-indomethacin system was composed to determine the proportions that can interact. Based on the “V” profile of the phase diagram in Fig. 2, the favipiravir-indomethacin system occurred at a molar ratio (1:2) or the fraction molar of favipiravir 0.33.

Hereafter we evaluated that composition to be an homogeneous preparation by solvent dropped grinding and than analysed it using the solid state instrument analysis. Visually combining the molar ratio (1:2) in absolute ethanol (v/v) produced particles that were softer than the initial compounds. Electrothermal measurements showed that the eutectic mixture system had a lower melting point than the individual components, namely 144 °C.

DSC analysis

DSC data confirmed that favipiravir melted at 192 °C and indomethacin at 162 °C, which aligned with the electrothermal data. Meanwhile, the (1:2) physical and SDG mixtures

Figure 3. DSC thermogram profile of favipiravir-indomethacin.

exhibited the lowest melting temperature among all compositions and single components, at 144 °C, as shown in Fig. 3.

Microscopy analysis

Microscopy analysis showed morphological changes, including: favipiravir appeared as needle-like crystals, indomethacin as fibrous structures, and the favipiravir-indomethacin mixture exhibited as a silk-like morphology. The results are presented in Fig. 4.

FTIR analysis (Fourier transform infrared)

The FTIR characterization of the favipiravir-indomethacin (1:2) mixture did not reveal any significant spectral shifts, indicating only forms an eutectics mixture. The spectra suggested only the presence of hydrogen bonding, likely from the amine groups in the favipiravir molecule. These results are shown in Fig. 5.

PXRD analysis (powder X-ray diffraction)

PXRD analysis showed that the diffractogram of favipiravir exhibited peaks at $2\theta = 12.1^\circ$, 19.94° , and 27.46° . Indomethacin displayed peaks at $2\theta = 10.4^\circ$, 11.4° , 16.49° , 19.9° , and 27.86° . The favipiravir-indomethacin (1:2) combination showed peaks at $2\theta = 8.45^\circ$, 11.73° , 14.6° ,

18.91° , 19.9° , and 27.86° . These data indicated that no chemical or physical reaction occurred in the system. The measurement results are shown in Fig. 6.

Spectrophotometry UV derivative development and validation

Derivative spectrophotometry was developed to separate the response of each drug in the mixture solution. First, the spectrum of each compound was recorded and then overlaid to check for overlap. The experiment identified a wavelength of 341 nm for favipiravir in the first derivative spectrum and 266 nm for indomethacin in the zero-order spectrum, as shown in Fig. 7.

Calibration curves were constructed after determining the clear spectrum with specific λ_{\max} values. Based on the spectra in Fig. 7, favipiravir absorbance was measured at the first derivative with $\lambda = 341$ nm, while indomethacin absorbance was measured at zero order with $\lambda = 266$ nm. The calibration curves for the zero and first derivatives are shown in Fig. 8a–d, respectively.

The calibration curve was determined by analyzing a series of standard solutions with concentrations of 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, and 60 ppm. Based on the absorption measurements of favipiravir single compound solutions at these concentrations, the linear equation obtained was $y = 0.0054x + 0.172$, with a correlation coefficient (R^2) of 0.9997. For the single compound indomethacin, the linear equation was $y = 0.0105x + 0.004$, with an R^2 value of 0.9979.

Figure 4. Analysis of an optical microscope.

Figure 5. FTIR spectra of favipiravir (blue), indomethacin (grey), physical mixture of favipiravir-indomethacin (1:2) (green), and the SDG product of favipiravir-indomethacin (1:2) (orange).

Figure 6. Analysis results from PXRD.

Figure 7. Zero derivative spectra of favipiravir (a) and indomethacin (b) and the overlay of the zero derivative spectra of favipiravir-indomethacin (c), which then was 1st derivative (d) ($n = 3$).

Figure 8. Calibration curve of favipiravir (a) and indomethacin (b) in a single component and favipiravir (c) and indomethacin (d) in the eutectic mixture ($n = 3$).

Analysis of solubility

Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 showed the solubility measurements of single compounds favipiravir and indomethacin and the favipiravir–indomethacin (1:2) eutectic compound.

Based on the data, the solubility of the single and eutectic mixture of favipiravir compound remained at 6 mg/L, whereas the solubility of indomethacin in the eutectic mixture increased approximately one hundred times compared to its single form.

SEM analysis

As showed in Fig. 11, SEM (scanning electron microscope) images presented photographs of the three samples—single-compound favipiravir, single-compound indomethacin, and the favipiravir-indomethacin 1:2 mixture—at 400 × magnification.

Discussion

This study combined favipiravir, a broad-spectrum antiviral agent, with indomethacin, a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID). The combination enhanced the solubility of both drugs, especially indomethacin, whose solubility increased one hundred fold compared to its single compound form, forming a eutectic point. This research aligned with the goals of pharmaceutical science.

A significant eutectic point was identified at a molar ratio of 1:2, where a new melting point of 144 °C appeared, significantly lower than the melting points of individual compounds (favipiravir at 192 °C and indomethacin at 162 °C). The formation of this eutectic point indicated

increased solubility in the combined compound relative to the individual drugs (Ferreira and Sarraguça 2024).

Initial analysis using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and electrothermal measurements revealed the change in melting point of the favipiravir-indomethacin combination. The resulting phase diagram formed a characteristic “V” shape (Dhoot et al. 2018).

Further investigation using Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) assessed the solid-state structure and chemical interactions of the combination. The PXRD diffractogram and FTIR spectra of the favipiravir-indomethacin mixture indicated that no new chemical structure was formed; the interaction between the two drugs was purely physical. This finding is advantageous for regulatory approval, as formulations that do not alter the chemical identity of the active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) may face fewer regulatory hurdles (Nugrahani et al. 2022).

In the solid mixture, the powder density changed compared to the individual compounds. The powder became finer when favipiravir and indomethacin were combined (Mayer 2020). Optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) confirmed this, showing that the 1:2 favipiravir-indomethacin mixture produced significantly smaller, more uniform particles. While single favipiravir appeared as needle-like crystals and indomethacin as fibrous structures, the mixture exhibited a silk-like morphology. The eutectic mixture of favipiravir-indomethacin exhibited a different morphology than the individual components, appearing more compact, homogeneous, and consisting of smaller particles than the single compounds (Ho 2022).

The developed UV-Vis derivative spectrophotometry method allowed clear separation of overlapping spectra

Figure 9. Solubility profile of single favipiravir (a), single indometacin (b), favipiravir in the eutectic mixture (c), and indomethacin in the eutectic mixture (d) (n = 3).

from the two drugs. The calibration curves were highly linear with R^2 values above 0.997, enhancing the reliability of solubility data and supporting potential applications in pharmacokinetic and dissolution studies (Rivai et al. 2018).

Data also showed that indomethacin's solubility increased 100-fold when mixed with favipiravir. This improvement was likely due to favipiravir enveloping the indomethacin particles after mixing by solvent-dropped

Figure 10. Solubility comparison between the single and eutectic mixture of favipiravir (a) and indomethacin (b).

Figure 11. Surface images of favipiravir—400x (a), indomethacin—400x (b), and favipiravir-indomethacin SDG-mixture—400x (c).

grinding. Electron microscope images showed a change in shape resembling indomethacin. Therefore, when exposed to water, favipiravir wetted first and subsequently reduced the surface tension of indomethacin, which was coated by favipiravir. The increase in solubility after eutectic mixing can be attributed to the formation of finer particles, which increased the surface area and enhanced contact with water (Andrusenko et al. 2021). Additionally, changes in the molecular environment surrounding the drugs likely caused low-energy interactions. In practice, a colloidal system formed when the eutectic mixture dissolved in water, consisting of microscopic particles that were difficult to separate from the saturated solution, even when using a fine pore filter (Whatman filter paper no. 42). Furthermore, after drying, the 1:2 favipiravir-indomethacin eutectic mixture particles became very soft and did not return to their original size and shape.

The increase in solubility is also expected to enhance the drug concentration in plasma, allowing more drug to reach their target and resulting in a faster onset of action. Therefore, the eutectic profile of this drug-drug binary system may be used to improve physicochemical properties, potentially producing a positive impact on therapeutic efficacy. Therapeutically, the favipiravir-indomethacin mixture holds great potential as an antiviral and anti-inflammatory treatment, which is particularly relevant for COVID-19, where controlling both viral replication and inflammatory cytokine response is critical for rapid therapeutic effect. Indomethacin's anti-inflammatory and antiviral properties, including inhibition of viral protein translation, further support this application (Tirelli et al. 2023).

Moreover, the physical nature of the favipiravir-indomethacin interaction—without forming a new chemical compound—indicates that rationally designed physical mixtures

can significantly improve drug physicochemical properties, facilitating their combination into solid dosage formulations.

Conclusion

Favipiravir and indomethacin form a eutectic mixture at 144 °C in a molar ratio of 1:2. Using solvent-dropped grinding (SDG), the mixture produces a homogeneous eutectic with smaller particle size. The solubility of favipiravir in the eutectic mixture does not change, compared to its single compound, while indomethacin's solubility increased one hundredfold compared to its single form. This phenomenon suggests promising opportunities for further research on drug combinations to treat viral infections, requiring both antiviral agents to control viral growth and anti-inflammatory drugs to manage inflammation.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

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The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

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Author contributions

Nugrahan I, Daryono HT, and Emy S: Compiling and designing experiments; conducting experiments; analyzing and interpreting data; Contributing reagents, materials, analytical tools, or data; Writing a term paper

Data availability

All of the data from the research are available in the text of this journal.

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